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PROBLEMS OF SOCIALIZATION IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: The article examines the problems of socialization in preschool-aged children, which represents a crucial stage in personality development. Key obstacles to successful socialization are identified, including a lack of parental communication, isolation from peers, the influence of digital technologies, excessive control or lack of attention, family conflicts, and difficulties in adapting to social groups. Proposed solutions include active parental involvement, fostering social skills, limiting the use of gadgets, creating a supportive family environment, and providing psychological and pedagogical support. The article emphasizes the importance of addressing these challenges early to ensure children's harmonious development and successful integration into society.

Key words: Socialization, preschool children, parent-child interaction, peer relationships, digital technologies, family environment, emotional development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiylashuv jarayonida yuzaga keladigan muammolar tahlil qilinadi. Bu bosqich shaxs rivojlanishida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Muvaffaqiyatli ijtimoiylashuvga to'sqinlik qiluvchi asosiy omillar sifatida ota-onalar bilan muloqotning yetishmasligi, tengdoshlar bilan aloqaning yo'qligi, raqamli texnologiyalarning ta'siri, ortiqcha nazorat yoki e'tiborsizlik, oilaviy nizolar va ijtimoiy guruhlariga moslashishdagi qiyinchiliklar keltirib o'tilgan. Muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun taklif etilgan yechimlar – ota-onalarning faol ishtiroki, ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish, gadgetlardan foydalanishni cheklash, qo'llab-quvvatlovchi oilaviy muhit yaratish hamda psixologik va pedagogik yordam ko'rsatishdan iborat. Maqolada bu muammolarni erta bosqichda hal qilish bolalarning uyg'un rivojlanishi va jamiyatga muvaffaqiyatli integratsiyasi uchun muhim ekani ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ijtimoiylashuv, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar, ota-ona va bola o'rtasidagi munosabat, tengdoshlar bilan aloqalar, raqamli texnologiyalar, oilaviy muhit, hissiy rivojlanish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются проблемы социализации детей дошкольного возраста, что представляет собой ключевой этап в развитии личности. Выявлены основные препятствия на пути успешной социализации, включая недостаток общения с родителями, изоляцию от сверстников, влияние цифровых технологий, чрезмерный контроль или недостаток внимания, семейные конфликты и трудности адаптации к социальным группам. Предложенные решения включают активное участие родителей, развитие социальных навыков, ограничение использования гаджетов, создание благоприятной семейной атмосферы, а также предоставление психологической и педагогической поддержки. В статье подчеркивается важность раннего устранения этих проблем для гармоничного развития ребенка и успешной интеграции в общество.

Ключевые слова: Социализация, дети дошкольного возраста, взаимодействие родителей и детей, отношения со сверстниками, цифровые технологии, семейная среда, эмоциональное развитие.

INTRODUCTION

The socialization of preschool children is a critical process that shapes their ability to function effectively in society. During the early years of life, children undergo rapid development in various areas, including language acquisition, emotional regulation, cognitive abilities, and social skills. It is in these formative years that children begin to learn the essential values, norms, and behaviors that will guide their future interactions with others. Socialization is not just about learning to interact with peers but also about understanding societal roles, developing empathy, and forming positive relationships with both adults and peers.

Preschool-aged children, typically between the ages of three and seven, are at a pivotal stage in their social development. This is a time when they begin to transition from the home environment—where they have been primarily cared for by family members—into a broader social environment, such as a kindergarten or daycare setting, where they are exposed to a variety of new experiences and social interactions.

It is during this period that children are expected to learn important skills such as sharing, cooperation, conflict resolution, and the ability to express their emotions in socially appropriate ways. However, this process is not without its challenges.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this context, understanding the problems and barriers to the socialization of preschool children is crucial for both parents and educators. By identifying these challenges and exploring effective strategies for fostering healthy social development, we can ensure that children are equipped with the necessary skills to navigate and succeed in an increasingly complex and interconnected world.

This article aims to explore the various factors influencing preschool children's socialization, identify the common challenges they face, and suggest practical solutions to support their social and emotional growth. Features of socialization in preschool children. Preschool age (3–7 years) is characterized by the intensive development of personality. During this period, children learn to interact with others, develop speech, master basic behavioral patterns, and begin to understand the rules governing social life. The main agents of socialization for preschoolers are:

- **Family** – Parents and close relatives play a primary role in shaping a child's behavior, values, and emotional stability.
- **Kindergarten** – Socialization occurs through interaction with peers, educators, and participation in group activities.
- **Social environment** – This includes contacts with family friends, neighbors, and other individuals outside the immediate family circle.

Despite the importance of this period, several factors may hinder proper socialization.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Modern life often leads to parents spending insufficient time with their children. Work, household responsibilities, and the use of gadgets reduce the amount and quality of live communication. This can result in speech delays, emotional instability, and difficulties in interacting with others. Some children do not attend kindergarten or have limited contact with other children. This hinders the development of communication, cooperation, and conflict-resolution skills, making it difficult for the child to establish social connections in the future. From an early age, children actively use phones, tablets, and other gadgets. While technologies can be beneficial, excessive use decreases live communication, negatively affecting socialization skills, empathy, and the understanding of others' emotions. Some parents excessively control their child, limiting their independence and opportunities to form social connections.

In other cases, children grow up in conditions of emotional or physical neglect, leading to difficulties in building trusting relationships. Conflicts between parents, lack of harmony, and even exposure to violence negatively impact a child's emotional state. Children in such environments may adopt destructive behavioral patterns, complicating their interactions with others. In kindergartens, children often face challenges adapting: fear of new surroundings, rejection by peers, and tense relationships with educators. These factors can cause stress and slow the process of socialization.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Ways to address the problems of socialization in preschool children. To ensure the successful socialization of preschool children, it is essential to recognize and address the various factors that may hinder their social development. Several strategies can be employed to overcome these challenges and support children's ability to form positive relationships, communicate effectively, and adapt to social settings. Below are some detailed solutions to the problems of socialization faced by preschoolers: Active Parental Involvement. Parents play a fundamental role in the early socialization of their children. Active involvement in a child's life, especially during the preschool years, is crucial to building emotional security and a strong sense of self. By engaging in meaningful interactions such as reading together, having conversations, playing, and participating in activities, parents can enhance their child's social and emotional development. Quality time: Set aside time each day for one-on-one interaction with the child, engaging in activities that foster emotional bonding, such as shared storytelling, problem-solving games, or simple discussions. Positive role modeling: Parents should model positive behaviors like empathy, kindness, and respect in everyday interactions.

Children are keen observers and often imitate the behavior they see at home. Encouraging Play and Peer Interaction. Play is one of the most powerful tools for socialization during the preschool years. Through play, children learn to share, cooperate, negotiate, and manage conflicts—all vital social skills that will serve them throughout their lives. Group play: Enroll children in group activities such as playdates, team sports, or preschool clubs, where they can interact with peers and practice socializing in a structured setting. These interactions help children build friendships and learn the importance of teamwork.

Role-playing games: Encourage children to engage in imaginative and role-playing activities, which allow them to explore different social roles and scenarios, such as “playing house” or acting out different characters. This builds empathy and perspective-taking skills. Reducing Dependence on Digital Devices. While digital technologies can be useful for educational purposes, excessive screen time can negatively impact a child’s social and emotional development. Overreliance on gadgets may limit opportunities for face-to-face interaction, thereby stunting the development of communication skills and empathy. Setting screen time limits: Create rules for limiting screen time, especially when it comes to passive activities like watching TV or playing video games.

Encourage more interactive and physically engaging activities such as outdoor play, arts and crafts, or building games. Creating a Supportive Family Environment. The home environment plays a significant role in a child’s ability to socialize effectively. A stable, emotionally supportive, and conflict-free home allows children to feel secure, which in turn makes it easier for them to form positive relationships outside the home. Emotional support: Parents should create an emotionally safe environment where children feel valued, understood, and supported. This enables children to develop confidence and the ability to express themselves openly. Preparation for Kindergarten and Social Settings.

Transitioning from home to a social environment like kindergarten can be challenging for many preschoolers. Preparing children for this transition can make the process smoother and less stressful. Gradual introduction: Before starting kindergarten, gradually introduce children to the new environment. Spend time visiting the school, meeting the teachers, and familiarizing children with the classroom setting. This reduces anxiety and helps children feel more confident in new situations. Social readiness skills: Teach children the basic social skills they will need in school, such as raising their hand, waiting their turn, and following simple instructions. Role-playing these behaviors can help children feel more comfortable when they are put into real-life situations.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The socialization of preschool children is a fundamental aspect of their overall development, laying the foundation for their ability to form meaningful relationships, adapt to new environments, and successfully integrate into society. While the process of socialization during early childhood can be fraught with challenges—such as limited parental interaction, peer isolation, and the overuse of digital technologies—these obstacles can be mitigated through targeted strategies and a supportive environment.

Active parental involvement, encouraging peer interaction through play, limiting screen time, and fostering a positive and emotionally supportive family atmosphere are all critical factors in promoting healthy socialization. Additionally, preparing children for transitions—such as entering kindergarten—and providing professional support when needed can help ensure that children develop the necessary skills for effective communication, empathy, and conflict resolution.

Ultimately, by addressing these issues early and offering tailored support, we can ensure that preschool children are equipped with the emotional intelligence and social skills needed to navigate the complexities of the modern world. A strong foundation of socialization during these formative years not only enhances children’s happiness and well-being, but also contributes to their long-term success in both personal and professional spheres.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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